

Simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of benzene in environmental samples

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A sensitive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of benzene based on nitration of benzene to 1,3-dinitrobenzene and its subsequent reduction to 1,3-phenylenediamine. The 1,3-phenylenediamine so formed is determined by diazotization-coupling reaction using 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene as coupling agent. The yellow orange azo dye formed in alkaline medium is measured spectrophotometrically at 415 nm. Beer's law is obeyed at 0.2–2.0 ppm benzene. The molar absorptivity is $3.07 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation are ± 0.01 and 1.62%, respectively, for 40 μg of benzene per 25 ml analyzed over 7 days. The method may be used to determine benzene in petrol vapour, coke oven effluent and cigarette smoke.

Various methods used for estimation of benzene are gas chromatography, IR and UV spectrophotometry, and colorimetry. The most commonly used colorimetric method is butanone method¹ based upon Janovsky reaction and formolite reaction. In this study a new and sensitive method is described for the determination of benzene. The method is based upon nitration and subsequent reduction of the dinitro compound to 1,3-phenylenediamine, which is diazotized and coupled with 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene to give a yellow orange azo dye in a strongly alkaline medium which is measured at 415 nm. It obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.2 to 2.0 ppm of benzene. The method is found to be much more sensitive than various reported methods^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

For nitration, concentrated nitric acid and sulfuric acid mixture (1 : 20, v/v) was used. The yield of 1,3-dinitrobenzene was found to be around 90%. The reduction of 1,3-dinitrobenzene required only 3 mg of zinc powder and 0.5–5.0 M HCl was used to maintain the acidity during diazotization. A 1 ml of sodium nitrite and 2 ml of 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene were required for maximum color intensity, excess nitrite was removed with the addition of sulfamic acid solution, and 1 ml of NaOH solution was sufficient for full color development. There was no significant change in the absorbance even if a large excess of 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene was taken. No appreciable deviation was observed in the absorbance value over the range 20–60° and the azo dye was stable for more than 72 h. Maximum absorbance values were observed at pH 11. Time required for coupling and full color development was 2 min each.

The yellow orange azo dye showed absorption maxima at 415 nm against the reagent blank. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 5–50 μg benzene per 25 ml of final solution (0.2–2.0 ppm) at 415 nm. Repeatability of the method was determined by the replicate analysis of the working standard solution containing 40 μg of benzene per 25 ml for 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were ± 0.01 and 1.62%, respectively. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $3.07 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0025 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

The effect of various species was studied. Most of the compounds such as aldehyde, phenol, ether, alcohol and common inorganic pollutants did not interfere with the proposed method. The tolerance limits (ppm) for various interferants are as follows : phosphate, urea (690); F^- , I^- , SO_4^{2-} , Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Sr^{II} (190); Ba^{II} , Pb^{II} , Fe^{III} , pyridine (140); phenol, methanol (90); Mg^{II} , Co^{II} (70); aniline, 1,2-dinitroaniline, formaldehyde (20), 1,3-dinitroaniline, 1,4-dinitronaphthylamine, 1-amino-2-naphthol (5). Ninety per cent absorption in the first impinger shows that the collection efficiency of the absorbing solution is almost 100% as 10% loss of benzene was observed during nitration step. The azo dye is extractable into isoamyl alcohol. Beer's law range was 0.02–0.20 ppm at 415 nm after extraction. The stability of the dye increases after extraction.

The method was applied successfully for the determination of benzene in petrol vapour, coke oven effluent and cigarette smoke.

Conclusion : The proposed method is selective, sensitive, reproducible and simple than the other spectrophotometric methods.

metric methods reported for benzene (Table 1). The azo dye is extractable, and therefore, this method can be successfully applied for the determination of trace amount of (0.02 ppm) benzene in various environmental samples.

Table 1. Comparison with other spectrophotometric method

Reagent	λ_{\max} nm	Beer's law range ppm	Remarks
Butanone ^a	620	0.5–1	Dye formed is stable for 5 min only.
α -Naphthol ^b	530	0.4–3.2	Less sensitive dye formed (stable for 30 h), method is not applicable for environmental samples.
Proposed method	415	0.2–2	More sensitive dye formed (stable over 72 h), method is applicable for environmental samples.

Experimental

A Systronic 108 UV-vis spectrophotometer, a Systronic 331 pH meter and a PIMCO calibrated rotameter were used.

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Deionized double-distilled water was used to prepare all solutions. Nitrating mixture (absorbing solution) was prepared from nitric acid (Merck) and sulfuric acid (Merck) in a ratio of 1 : 20 (v/v)³. Purified ether solvent (Merck) freed from peroxide and aldehyde was used³. A 0.1% stock solution of benzene (Sisco-chem) was prepared in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1, v/v). A working standard solution was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock. Sodium nitrite solution (Merck) a working standard containing 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, was prepared from a 0.1% aqueous solution of sodium nitrite. A

0.01 M aqueous solution of 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene (Loba Chimie), was used. 5 M aqueous solution NaOH (Merck), a 3% solution of sulfamic acid and a 10% solution of EDTA were used.

Procedure : A modified Wilson's procedure was used for the absorption of benzene^{4,5}. An aliquot of standard solution of benzene (5–50 μg) along with air was absorbed in two impingers containing 10 ml of nitrating mixture and 1,3-dinitrobenzene formed was reduced to 1,3-phenylenediamine in the presence of zinc dust (3 mg) and 5 M HCl (1 ml). Then sodium nitrite solution (1 ml) was added to it and the mixture shaken gently for 2 min. During diazotization, acidity was maintained by 0.5–5.0 M HCl. Sulfamic acid (1 ml) was then added to remove any excess nitrite and metals ions were masked by adding EDTA (1 ml). 1,3,5-Trihydroxybenzene (2 ml) was added for coupling in alkaline medium. The mixture was set aside for 2 min, then made up to the mark with water and the absorbance of the yellow orange coloured azo dye was measured at 415 nm against a reagent blank.

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